

Resonant transducers with nanostructural based birefringence for the selective monitoring of VOCs in ambient conditions

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Abstract

Conventional porous 1D Bragg Microcavities are known to optically respond to vapour adsorption and condensation in their pores, but are unable to identify a specific compound or to accurately work under the interference of environmental moisture. In this work, we have developed a new kind of nanocolumnar birefringent Bragg microcavity (BBM) that, tailored by oblique angle deposition, behave as selective transducer of volatile organic compounds (VOCs). Unlike the atomic lattice origin of birefringence in single crystals, birefringence in the BBMs stems from an anisotropic organization at the nanoscale of their structural elements and void space. The optical adsorption isotherms recorded upon exposure of these nanostructured systems to water vapour and VOCs have revealed a rich yet unexplored phenomenology linked to their birefringence that provides both capacity for vapour identification and partial pressure determination. This photonic response has been reproduced with a theoretical model accounting for the evolution of birefringence of the individual layers upon vapour condensation in nanopores and inter-nanocolumnar void. BBMs that repelled water but were accessible to VOCs have been also developed through the grafting of their internal surfaces with perfluorooctyltriethoxysilane molecules. These nanostructured photonic systems are proposed for the development transducers that, operating in environmental conditions, may respond specifically to a given VOC-

Keywords: Nanostructured multilayers, nanostructural birefringence, Bragg microcavity, nanoporosity, optical adsorption isotherms, grafting functionalization, optical VOC monitoring, OAD.

1.- INTRODUCTION

Photonic structures made of hierarchical structured nanosheets¹ (5b), flexible metal-organic framework stacks (5c) or inspired by nature (5a) have been proposed as optical transducers of vapour pressure. More specifically, porous 1D photonic structures in the form of Bragg mirrors and Bragg microcavities, these later also designated as monolithic Fabry-Perot resonators, have been proposed for sensor (1, 2) and other detection and responsive applications (3-5, 5a). The capacity of these photonic structures to interact with the medium relies on an easy accessibility of vapours or liquids to their void space and on the photonic changes induced by the incorporation of a condensable or liquid phase in their structure. Hence, a reliable photonic response of these systems requires a strict control at the nanoscale of the constituent structural elements and accessible porosity (4, 5). In the present work, we propose the usage of a new kind of nanocolumnar birefringent Bragg Microcavity (BBM) (6) which, prepared by oblique angle deposition (OAD) (7, 7a), is capable of both optically determining the partial pressure of vapours and identifying their chemical nature. Contrary to the crystal lattice based birefringence in anisotropic single crystals or the birefringence in monolithic Fabry_Perot resonators stemming from the vertical modulation of refractive index of stacked layers of polymers (10), optical anisotropy in these nanostructured BBMs results from the self-organization at nanometric scale of the nanocolumns and voids defining their microstructure. Optically anisotropic nanocolumnar systems have been previously proposed for the development of switchable radial polarization vector converters (8), or sensors for liquids and solutions (8a, 8b, 8c).

Various optical detection principles have been proposed with nanostructured Bragg mirrors and 1D-BMs that, in most cases, entail the recording of a red shift in the position of their reflection band gap or resonant peak, respectively (9). Advanced examples of physical mechanisms inducing these optical changes, include the filling of pores with liquids or vapours (11), the swelling by vapour adsorption of one layer component stacked in the photonic crystal (12) or the modulation in the intensity of the emission of a

fluorophore ion due to the swelling of the defect layer of a microcavity (13). However, despite the usage of advanced monitoring principles and the application of sophisticated “in silico” modelling to account for the optical changes (13), classical nanostructured systems do not present a selective response and, though they can follow concentration changes in liquids (14) or the adsorption of a vapour (1,2), they cannot differentiate the type of liquid solution or identify the chemical nature of the adsorbed vapour. Other classical strategies developed some years ago for vapour and liquid detection using nanostructured porous silicon 1-D photonic systems also failed to selectively identify a given compound (17) though, for biomolecular applications, selective detection of minority components in a fluid has been achieved via pore surface functionalization with molecules with proved specificity towards a target compound (18,19).

A classical methodology for volatile organic compound (VOC) monitoring with 1-D photonic structures, particularly 1D-BMs, consists of recording a so-called optical adsorption isotherm. This procedure has been used for porosity characterization in nanostructured multilayers (20-22) and photonic sensor applications, in this latter case using sculptured photonic structures prepared by OAD (23-24). An optical adsorption isotherm is obtained plotting the red-shift of the BM resonant peak with respect to the vapour pressure. These optical isotherms are similar in shape to those obtained with other layered or powder materials by means of either volumetric or gravimetric methods (25, 27). Basic assumption to interpret an optical isotherm is that, according to effective medium theories, filling the void volume with condensed vapours produces a change in the effective refractive index of the stacked layers and therefore a red-shift of the resonant peak. This and similar optical principles of operation with porous thin films/multilayers have been proposed to monitor relative humidity or the partial pressure of a specific vapour as a function of temperature (29).

The nanostructured BBMs utilized in this work consist of a stack of SiO₂ and TiO₂ nanocolumnar layers with a zigzag configuration prepared by e-beam OAD (6). A singular feature of these individual nanocolumnar layers is their birefringent behaviour characterized by a distinct optical response depending on light polarization and electric field vector orientation with respect to the main optical axis of the system. This unique optical property has been systematically exploited in the first part of the work for the analysis of VOCs. In particular, we prove that the optical adsorption isotherms measured with the BBM and unpolarised light contain a richer information than that found in

isotherms recorded with conventional 1D-BMs and that their analysis permits both determining vapour pressure (i.e., with respect to saturation) and type of adsorbed vapour. Moreover, we show that through the optical simulation of the vapour adsorption/condensation behaviour in the BBMs it is possible to describe the filling mechanism of the void nanostructures (i.e., nano- or meso-pores with sizes smaller or higher than 2 nm, respectively (26)). In the second part of the work we show that the chemical grafting of the perfluorooctyltriethoxysilane (PFOTES) molecule (29, 29a) onto the internal surfaces of voids in the BBM renders a water repellent system that precludes the adsorption and condensation of moisture. We show that this procedure opens the way for the selective detection of VOCs and therefore to the development of label free photonic vapour sensors usable in ambient conditions.

2.- RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

2.1. Nanostructure and optical behaviour of BBM

The BBMs consisted of two nanostructured Bragg mirrors separated by another nanocolumnar central layer (cavity). The Bragg mirrors were fabricated by the successive stacking of SiO₂ and TiO₂ porous nanocolumnar thin films by OAD at 70° deposition angle. The Bragg mirrors had a HLHLHLH multilayer structure, where H/L represents a high/low refractive index layer (i.e., TiO₂/SiO₂). The central cavity consisted of a low refractive index layer. Azimuthally turning the substrate by 180° after deposition of each layer rendered a zigzag columnar microstructure and a homogeneous thickness over relatively large areas. A more detailed description of the synthesis and some basic characterization analysis of these BBM can be found in the materials and method section and in a previous publication, where we show a preliminary analysis of the multilayer nanostructural arrangement that gives rise to the birefringence of the system (6).

Figure 1 shows FIB-SEM cross section micrographs of a typical BBM sample taken after sectioning the structure either parallel (a) or perpendicular (b) to the deposition plane (see schemes of the deposition geometry in **Figure S1** of Supporting Information). In previous works on similar of OAD multilayers it has been estimated that the void fraction of this type of materials is about 35-40% of their total volume (30). According to Figure 1a), the zigzag microstructure of this BBM consists of a different material every segment and is

formed by separated tilted nanocolumns that leave a considerable empty space among them. Moreover, the cross section in Figure 1b taken along the direction perpendicular to the deposition plane shows a comparatively more homogeneous distribution of material within each layer, suggesting a higher material connectivity in this direction. The top view SEM micrograph in Figure 1c), showing that the nanocolumns are preferentially connected in the direction perpendicular to the deposition plane, confirms the existence of a lateral association among nanocolumns and provides a clue to account for the structural birefringence of the BBMs. In a previous work we have shown that this lateral association extends through the whole multilayer thickness, i.e., it passes from one material segment to the next within the zigzag microstructure. We have named this lateral nanocolumnar association extending through the whole multilayer as “fence-bundling” (6). A basic assumption in this work is that this anisotropic arrangement of nanocolumns and, more precisely, the preferential material association in the direction perpendicular to the deposition plane, induces a strong structural in-plane birefringence in the individual layers with a fast (slow) main optical axis in the direction perpendicular (parallel) to fence-bundling direction \mathbf{b} (see Figure 1c). We must emphasize that this birefringence is not linked to the crystalline structure of the stacked materials (amorphous in a crystallographic sense), but to the anisotropic microstructure resulting from the lateral association of nanocolumnar units with a size in the order of tens of nanometers. This anisotropy in nanometric dimensions confers a different macroscopic polarizability along each main perpendicular direction in the system.

Figure 1d shows the optical transmittance spectra of the BBM taken at normal incidence using either unpolarised light (full line) or polarised light with its electric field aligned either parallel (orange dashed line) or perpendicular (green dotted line) to the fence-bundling direction. The spectra consist of a resonant transmitted feature at 1.95-2.15 eV (i.e., 580-620 nm) within the wide reflection band of 1.7-2.3 eV (530-720 nm) characteristic of the two Bragg mirrors integrated in the BBM. The transmittance spectra acquired with polarised light with its electric field aligned parallel/perpendicular to the fast/slow optical axis of the BBM depict a single peak, while it consists of a double peak when using unpolarised light. The separation w'_r between the two single peaks recorded with linear polarized light, or the full width at half maximum (FWHM) w_r of the double resonant peak, can be taken as a measure of the strength of the optical activity of the multilayer system. Since this latter parameter is linked to the in-plane birefringence of the

individual layers within the multilayer stack, we designate w_r as *birefringence strength* parameter. We will use it for the analysis of vapour adsorption together with the mean position of the double resonant peak x_r that, defined here as *filling* parameter, is the classical parameter used in literature to monitor optical adsorption isotherms (22-25). For comparison, we will also use the position and w_r' FWHM of the individual resonant peaks acquired with linear polarised light with the electric field vector \mathbf{E} aligned parallel (perpendicular) to the sample fence-bundling direction (in the following designated as \mathbf{b}), that will be named in the text as $x_{r\parallel}$ ($x_{r\perp}$) and $w_{r\parallel}$ ($w_{r\perp}$), respectively.

Figure 1. FIB-SEM cross section micrographs of the BBM taken at two magnification scales along a direction parallel (a) or perpendicular (b) to the deposition plane. c) SEM top view micrograph showing the bundling association in one direction at the surface of the nanocolumns and the slow and fast optical axes (parallel and perpendicular to the fence-bundling direction, respectively). The red arrow in this figure indicates the direction of incoming material flux during deposition. d) Transmittance at normal incidence using incident unpolarised light (full line), or polarised light with the electric field vector aligned parallel (dashed line) or perpendicular (dotted line) to fence-bundling \mathbf{b} direction. (barras de escala)

2.2. Optical adsorption isotherms and birefringence in nanostructured BBM

The spectra shown in Figure 1d were taken for a pristine BBM and dry conditions, i.e., with its void space empty or, more precisely, filled with air. According to effective medium theories, a reasonable assumption is that the effective refraction index of each stacked layer varies as its void space is partially or completely filled with condensed vapours. This behaviour has been extensively studied in conventional porous BM (6,11-17, 20-25). Working with the BBM, it might be possible that the difference in polarizability along the fast and slow optical axis also varies upon vapour adsorption. To check this point and to fully characterize the optical response of the BBM to the adsorption/condensation of vapours we have followed the changes in the *filling* and *birefringence strength* parameters x_r and w_r (for comparison also the evolution of $x_{r\perp}$ and $w_{r\perp}$) measured in the spectra recorded with unpolarised (linear polarised) light as a function of the relative vapour pressure P/P_0 ratio, where P_0 is the saturation partial pressure at room temperature. Results of these experiments are reported in **Figures 2** (with linear polarized light) and **3** (with unpolarized light) using water vapour as adsorbent.

The scheme in Figure 2a shows that the electrical polarization vector of the light impinges parallel to the fenced bundling direction of the BBM (i.e., $\mathbf{E} \perp \mathbf{b}$) in this experiment. The series of transmittance spectra in Figure 2b) recorded under these conditions show a strong variation of the position $x_{r\perp}$, and a less intense one of the width $w_{r\perp}$ of the resonant feature as a function of the relative partial pressure of water. The plot of these parameters as a function of P/P_0 in Figure 2c gives rise to two curves, where that corresponding to x_r vs. P/P_0 clearly reproduces the shape of a typical type IV adsorption isotherm according to the IUPAC classification (25,31). In powder materials, as well as in the investigated BBM, this particular shape can be attributed to the progressive filling of pores of different sizes with condensed vapour: at low P/P_0 values (up to ca. 0.1 in the curve of Figure 2c) nanopores with a size smaller than 2 nm become filled with condensed water vapour, followed by a progressive adsorption and condensation onto large mesopores (P/P_0 range between ~ 0.1 and ~ 0.6) and their eventual filling with liquid in the interval between ~ 0.6 and 1.0 (25,31). Similar optical isotherm curves have been reported for porous and optically isotropic 1D-BMs prepared by a large variety of procedures (20-25). For 1D-BM prepared by OAD (23-25), these curves have been used for the development of humidity and other vapour sensors. Figure 2c also shows the evolution of the $w_{r\perp}$

parameter obtained from the resonant features in Figure 2b as a function of P/P_0 . This curve shows that the width of the resonant feature remains unchanged up to a partial pressure of approximately 0.6, followed by an increase by ca. a 10 %, to finally decrease again as P/P_0 approaches 1. A similar behaviour was also found for other vapours and will be discussed further in section 2.3. We advance though that we do not associate the observed trend to a change in birefringence (optical activity) of the system that, by no means, would be accessible using linearly polarized light to record the spectra.

Figure 2. a) Scheme showing the interaction of linear polarized light with the fence-bundled associated structure of nanocolumns in the BBM. b) Normalized transmittance spectra acquired at normal incidence with linear polarized light with $E \perp \mathbf{b}$ for increasingly higher relative water partial pressures P/P_0 . c) Optical adsorption isotherm obtained representing the peak position $x_{r\perp}$ and plot of FWHM $w_{r\perp}$ vs. P/P_0 .

A richer phenomenology was found when optical adsorption isotherms were acquired using unpolarized light. **Figure 3a** shows a scheme of the interaction of the unpolarized light with the fence-bundled structure of the BBM. In Figure 3b) we show the transmittance spectra recorded upon exposure of the BBM to increasing P/P_0 values of water vapour. This series of spectra reveals that the position of the resonant double peak (i.e., the *filling* parameter x_r , as defined in Figure 1) progressively red-shifts as P/P_0

increases. Besides, the double-peak progressively merges into a single peak and w_r (birefringence strength parameter) decreases. As for the results in Figure 2, we attribute these two effects to the adsorption and progressive filling of the BBM pores with condensed water. Plotting the values of x_r and w_r as a function of P/P_0 renders two rather symmetrical curves that can be taken as optical adsorption isotherms for this kind of nanostructured BBM. We advance that each curve reflects a different physical phenomenon (pore filling degree and variation of birefringence) and that their comparison provides a way to identify the vapour adsorbed in the pores.

Figure 3. a) Scheme showing the interaction of unpolarized light with the fence-bundled associated structure of nanocolumns in the BBM. b) Normalized transmittance spectra acquired at normal incidence with unpolarized light for increasing relative water partial pressures P/P_0 . c) Optical adsorption isotherms showing the evolution of the filling x_r and birefringence strength parameter w_r of the resonant feature as a function of P/P_0 . d) Plot of w_r vs x_r for increasing P/P_0 values (some values are indicated in the plot for guidance). Two values of the Birefringence damping rate parameter $\Delta w_r / \Delta x_r$, defined by the slopes of two straight lines can be deduced from this plot. They correspond to two different adsorption regimes (see text).

In particular, the observed behaviour in Figures 3b and 3c) reveals that progressive vapour adsorption/condensation produces both the progressive filling of the void space in the BBM as evidenced by the increase of x_r and a progressive loss of optical activity as evidenced by the decrease of w_r . The direct dependence between a parameter that reflects the optical activity of the BBM and the vapour pressure supports the possibility of manufacturing optically polarization active devices where birefringence would be tuned by water adsorption/infiltration. Remarkably, according to Figure 3d where w_r is plotted against x_r , the *filling* and *birefringence strength* parameters do not relate each other according to a single relationship, but according to two linear correlations with a change in slope at $P/P_0 = 0.68$, i.e. close at the relative vapour pressure at which condensation filling of mesopores begins in these BBM (see section 2.3). We define as *birefringence damping rate* the slope $\Delta w_r/\Delta x_r$ deduced from this plot at high partial pressures. Thus, for P/P_0 between 0.00 and 0.68, progress in adsorption only produces a relatively slight decrease in optical activity characterized by a slope of 0.17. However, from this P/P_0 value upwards the decrease in optical activity progresses about 3 times faster and renders a slope (*birefringence damping rate*) of 0.53.

Besides water, a series of VOCs compounds were also investigated using the same methodology. The investigated vapours included methanol, ethanol, heptane, chloroform and toluene, each compound characterized by a different saturation partial pressure P_0 , refractive indices, surface energy in their condensed phases and dipole moment (see Table 1). Despite these differences, their adsorption/condensation optical isotherms followed a similar trend than that reported for water, either with polarized or unpolarised light. In the supporting information, **Figures S2**, we show the series of optical adsorption isotherms measured with unpolarized light for the examined VOCs, all of them characterized by a type IV shape, according to IUPAC (24). Interestingly, a thorough analysis of these isotherms, including the determination of *birefringence damping rate* parameters, provides a means for their identification. In fact, the w_r vs. x_r plots in **Figure 4** show that for $P/P_0 > 0.6$ they present a different slope for each vapour. This means that *the birefringence damping rate parameter $\Delta w_r/\Delta x_r$ at high partial pressures is a compound selective parameter that can be used to identify vapours with BBMs*. **Table 1** gathers the values of the experimental total red-shifts $|x_{ri} - x_{rf}|$ and the *birefringence damping rates* $\Delta w_r/\Delta x_r$ determined for the different vapours. At first sight, a direct correlation can be

established between the refractive index of the examined VOCs and the experimentally determined $|x_{ri} - x_{rf}|$ and $\Delta w_r/\Delta x_r$ values, suggesting that these two parameters might be used for VOC identification. For practical applications though, we disregard the former because it can be affected by experimental problems such as an undefined termination of the adsorption process (i.e., P_f can be smaller than P_0), an undefined volume of the meniscus that according to the Kelvin law of capillary adsorption form in the mesopores (26, 32), and the fact that it will depend on the total void volume of the BBM and therefore affected by manufacturing variables. These problems do not affect the *birefringence damping rate* parameter that, through its correlation with the refractive index value of he condensed vapor, we propose as a straightforward means of VOC identification. We must note that in table 1, heptane deviates from the direct correlation found between n and $\Delta w_r/\Delta x_r$ for the rest of vapours. We attribute this exception to the null polarizability of this molecule and the fact that its optical adsorption isotherm slightly deviates from the typical shape of the type IV (see supporting information S2). However, this does not withstand the fact that each VOC compound is characterized by a specific *birefringence damping rate* that can be used for identification.

Figure 4. Plots of the birefringent strength w_r vs. filling x_r parameters measured in the transmittance spectra of BBM acquired with unpolarised light at normal incidence during the adsorption of water, methanol, ethanol, heptane, chloroform and toluene.

Table 1.- Comparison of several physical magnitudes (saturation vapour pressure, refractive index, surface energy, and dipolar moment) and the experimental value of the total red-shift and birefringence damping rate parameters for $P/P_0 > 0.6$ determined from the optical adsorption isotherms acquired with unpolarised light at normal incidence for the selected VOCs. For heptane, values taken for the F-BBM structures are also included

	Adsorbed vapour					
	water	methanol	ethanol	heptane	chloroform	toluene
Sat. vapour pressure @ 20°C, 1 atm (kPa)	2.4	13	5.8	5.3	26	2.8
Refractive index	1.33	1.33	1.36	1.39	1.45	1.50
Surface energy (mN/m)	72.8	22.7	22.1	20.1	27.5	28.4
Dipolar moment (D)	1.85	1.70	1.69	0.00	1.04	0.36
Total red shift $x_{ri} - x_{rf}$ (eV/nm) (experimental)	0.15/41	0.16/44	0.16/44	0.18/50 (F-BBM 0.17/47)	0.20/56	0.21/59
Birefringence damping rate $\Delta w_r/\Delta x_r$ (experimental) errorbars !!!	0.530	0.418	0.396	0.443 ± 0.01) (F-BBM 0.403± 0.005)	0.352	0.325

2.3. Simulation of the adsorption dependent optical activity of BBM

The evolution of the filling x_r , birefringence strength w_r and birefringence damping rate $\Delta w_r/\Delta x_r$ parameters upon progressive vapour adsorption in the BBM for a given VOC has been simulated with a parameterized optical model that incorporates the possibility that the refractive indexes along the two orthogonal main optical axes (i.e., ||-bundling and \perp -bundling) of the films in the multilayer stack can be varied independently. This permits to simulate a distinct evolution of polarizability, and therefore refractive index, along each main optical axis of the BBM as a function of the filling factor, defined as the overall percentage of void volume of the BBM filled with condensed vapour.

Simulations have been carried out for three adsorption/condensation situations: i) assuming that the variation of refractive index with the pore filling fraction complies with

a single-stage process, whereby both filling factor and refraction indexes vary according to an equivalent linear trend along the two optical axes until the condensate fills completely the empty space in the BBM (*one-stage* model simulation); ii) and iii) assuming that the variation of refractive index along each direction, directly linked to the pore filling rate along that axis, follows a two-stage process; in the first stage, up to filling ca. 30% of the available void space, the filling rate along the \parallel -bundling direction increases linearly either 1.3 (ii) or 2.0 (iii) faster than along the \perp -bundling direction, (*two-stages-1.3* or *two-stages-2.0* model simulations); in the second stage, for a pore filling fraction above 30%, the filling rate varies linearly and evenly in the two directions until completing the filling of pores. For these three simulation models, the evolution of filling rates along each orthogonal optical axis as a function of pore filling fraction are represented in **Figure S4**. Figure 5a shows a series of simulated spectra obtained under the assumption of *one-stage* model. Remarkably, these simulated spectra reproduce well the evolution of experimental spectra (c.f. Figure 2a) depicting a red shift and a progressive merging of the two resonant peak components that are similar to the experimental trends (c.f., Figure 3). A similar evolution of spectra was obtained for the *two-stages* models (spectra not shown). However, differences were found when plotting x_r vs w_r depending on the model utilized to simulate the experiment. For water and heptane, Figure 5b shows that the curves obtained for the *two-stages-1.3* model present a similar shape than the experimental ones (c.f., Figures ...) and that only the slopes of the curves of the *two-stages-1.3* model for $P/P_0 > 0,6$ reproduce well the experimental value of the *birefringence damping rate* $\Delta w_r / \Delta x_r$ of the different VOCs.

Figure 5. a) Transmission spectra around the resonant peak of the BBM calculated according to the one-stage model for increasing filling fractions (see text). b) Plots of w_r against x_r as the filling fraction increases for the three model simulations and water and heptane as examples. c) Pictorial representation of the filling process of the open void structure of the BBM with condensed vapours. Each step shows a pictorial image of a cross section of the multilayer structure, with column bundling in the direction perpendicular to the drawings. Step-0: evacuated empty pore structure. step-1: initial condensation in nanopores within the nanocolumns. step-2: complete filling of nanopores within the nanocolumns and initial surface adsorption in the mesopores taken as the void space in-between associated nanocolumns. step-3: initial filling of mesopores and meniscus formation in-between associated nanocolumns. step-4: complete filling of the pore structure.

The previous simulations provide a clear insight about the evolution of the adsorption process in the BBM and its dependence on nanostructure. According to the scheme in Figure 5c, two pore condensation processes are expected to occur in order to account for the two $\Delta w_r/\Delta x_r$ slope values determined experimentally (c.f. Figure 4) and predicted theoretically for the *two-stages-1.3* model (c.f. Figure 5b)). Drawings in this scheme represent a cross section of the zig-zag multilayer, where the fence-bundling direction is perpendicular to the page. This scheme is an oversimplification of the real BBM nanostructure where pore and neck sizes would present a wide variation. Step-0 in this series of diagrams represents the initial situation for the empty BBM where both the small nanopores and the void space among nanocolumns are empty. According to a recent work

using positron annihilation spectroscopy (32) nanopores of 2 nm or smaller distribute within the nanocolumns. We define the empty space among nanocolumns as mesopores (pore size larger than 2nm (25)). Mesopores in the BBM extend from the interface with the substrate up to the external surface (c.f., Figure 1). Step-1 represents the initial steps of the adsorption process when vapour condenses in the nanopores (i.e. first step up to P/P_0 equal ~ 0.1 in the experimental spectra and isotherms in Figures 3 and 4 and initial simulated spectra in Figure 5a). This is the expected situation deduced from the basic principles of Kelvin adsorption that are assumed in common models of type IV adsorption isotherms (25,26, 31). Since nanopores are mainly distributed within the nanocolumns, their filling with condensed liquids will contribute to increase the polarizability along the bundling direction \mathbf{b} , and therefore to increase the effective refractive index more rapidly in this direction than in the orthogonal direction. This agrees with the chosen two-stage model description of the refraction index variation along the two main directions of the system.

In step-2, vapour adsorption starts in the mesopores where a thin layer of condensed vapour would form along the whole void structure. This stage would roughly correspond to a P/P_0 interval comprised between 0.1 and 0.6 (c.f., Figure 3 and Figures S2 in supporting information) and would be favoured by the fact that the lateral walls of nanocolumns are rough and may even present open entrances with sizes in the order of 2 nm (see Figure 1a-c and the enlargements in Figure 5c)). Then, for increasing vapour pressures, a liquid column terminated in a meniscus with a radius controlled by the Kelvin equation (25, 26, 31) develops from the bottom of the mesopores (step-3, note that mesopores filling can be heterogeneous in height depending of intercolumnar distance and that a meniscus might also form at neck narrowing points between nanocolumns). In step-4, roughly in the P/P_0 interval between 0.6 and 1.0, filling will be eventually completed. Besides agreeing with the two-stage model, this simple scheme accounts for the evolution of the optical activity of the BBM with P/P_0 and permits to propose an explanation for the different *birefringence damping rate* values found for each VOCs. Effectively, basic assumption by the simulations is that the distinct values of *birrefringent damping rate* $\Delta w_r/\Delta x_r$ represent a measurement of the efficiency of the condensed liquid to damp the difference in refractive index between the two main optical axis in the empty BBM and that the refractive index value of the condensed liquids is the main variable

accounting for this effect (see Materials and Methods section for details about model calculations).

Incidentally, the simplified model in Figure 5c) also explains the observation of a transitory increase in the $w_{r\perp}$ parameter of the single resonant peak detected for $P/P_0 > 0.6$ when the spectra are recorded with linearly polarized light (c.f., Figure 2 and Figure S3 in supporting info). In the frame of the classical Kelvin concepts (31) for capilarity condensation in pores and formation of a meniscus, filling state of mesopores can be quite different in step 3, so that thinner mesopores might be almost filled while thicker ones may still be at the initial stages of the filling process. Neck narrowing and other heterogeneities might also contribute to a heterogeneous condensation. We attribute the transitory increase in the width of the resonant peak to this heterogeneity in the filling process and not to any effect related with the system birefringence.

2.4. Sequential water/VOC vapour adsorption in the BBM

In previous sections, we have shown that the BBM can identify a particular VOCs through the evaluation of the *birefringence damping rate* $\Delta w_r/\Delta x_r$ parameter. However, vapour adsorption into the BBM is in principle not selective and the use of a BBM in ambient conditions as photonic sensor of VOCs would be affected by the adsorption of water moisture from the environment. In the quest for a solution of this problem, we have firstly investigated to which extent water vapour may affect the adsorption of a VOC and vice-versa. The following experiment was carried out to this end: i) firstly we dosed water vapour up to a partial pressure $P/P_0(\text{water}) = 0.8$ (i.e., according to Figure 2 at this vapour pressure void filling factor reaches approximately ...%) and then heptane vapour up to saturation $P/P_0(\text{heptane}) = 1$; ii) then, after pumping removal of the condensed vapours, we performed the experiment in the reverse order, we firstly dosed heptane up to a partial pressure of $P/P_0(\text{heptane}) = 0.8$ and then water vapour up to saturation $P/P_0(\text{water}) = 1.0$. The results of this sequential adsorption experiments are reported in **Figure 6** where we have plotted the evolution of the *filling* x_r and *birefringence strength* w_r parameters as a function of the relative partial pressure of each vapour. The included scheme represents an idealized cross section view of mesopores and their partial filling with water and/or heptane in each experiment. As expected, in the step i) the profile of the water isotherm (Figure 6a) coincides with that reported in Figure 3b. Then, the adsorption/condensation

of heptane seems to continue smoothly up to reach saturation at $P/P_0(\text{heptane})=1$. Remarkably, the *birefringence damping rate* parameter due to heptane adsorption is about the same (i.e., 0.44) than that obtained when heptane adsorbed directly into the bare BBM (0.43, see SI Figure ...). However, the reverse experiment renders a completely different result: despite that partial pressure of heptane has not reached saturation and therefore the pores are not completely filled with condensed liquid, exposing the BBM to progressively higher partial pressures of water until saturation (i.e., $P/P_0(\text{water}) = 1$) does not affect either x_r or w_r . In other words, adsorbing a certain amount of heptane precludes the adsorption of water vapour, although the opposite does not apply. Interestingly, this behaviour was only observed with water vapour but not with other vapours (e.g., ethanol, methanol, toluene, chloroform, etc.), a result that, in agreement with the Kelvin concepts about the influence of liquid surface tension on condensation (31), points to the high value of the surface tension of water (c.f. Table 1) as responsible for this differential behaviour.

Figure 6. a) Evolution of filling and birefringence strength parameters of a BBM sequentially exposed to increasing vapour pressures of first water and then heptane. b) Plot of w_r vs. x_r taken from figure a). c) Evolution of filling and birefringence strength parameters of a BBM sequentially exposed to increasing vapour pressures of first heptane and then water.

2.5. Selective adsorption of VOCs into functionalized F-BBM

The fact that heptane pre-adsorption precludes the adsorption of water suggests that modifying the pore surface of the BBM with water repellent functional groups/molecules might permanently hinder water adsorption. To prove this hypothesis we functionalized the pore surfaces of the BBM with PFOTES molecules following the grafting procedure reported in the experimental section. The obtained fluorine functionalised BBM (F-BBM) presented a homogeneous distribution of F along the whole thickness as verified by the depth profile XPS analysis. **Figure 7** shows that in-depth fluorine distribution was homogeneous from the surface to the interface with the substrate, while the distribution of Ti and Si followed the periodicity of TiO₂ and SiO₂ stacked layers reported in Figure 2. The constant in-depth distribution of F proves that the PFOTES molecules have become homogeneously grafted at the void inner surface through the whole thickness of the F-BBM. The scheme in Figure 7 represents a cartoon with a description of the distribution of molecules into the pores. Interestingly, while the surface of BBM was hydrophilic and presented a water contact angle of 20°, that of F-BBM was hydrophobic

and had a water contact angle of 125° that sustains a hydrophobic behaviour and a significant repulsion towards water (33).

Figure 7. a) XPS in-depth profile of a F-BBM sample grafted with PFOTES molecules. C, F, Si and Ti content was evaluated from C1s, F1s, Si2p, and Ti2p signals, corrected by the corresponding sensitivity factors, respectively. B) Scheme of the grafting of the PFOTES molecules on the pore surfaces of the F-BBM

Water repulsion upon adsorption/condensation was further confirmed optically since no change in the shape of the transmission spectrum of the F-BBM was found upon exposure to water vapour even for $P/P_0 = 1$ (i.e., at saturation conditions). However, VOCs and other vapours investigated in this work, including ethanol or methanol that present some similarities with water, did adsorb in the F-BBM and gave rise to isotherms very similar, though not identical, in shape, than those recorded for the bare BBM (c.f., Figure S..S). We attribute these slight changes to that grafted PFOTES molecules prevent the adsorption of VOCs in the nanopores, but practically leave unaffected their adsorption in the mesopores. For example, a change in the shape of the adsorption isotherm is clearly observed for heptane, whose analysis is presented in **Figure 8**. Now the isotherm shape approaches that of type III according to the IUPAC (26) where it has disappeared the initial adsorption step for $P/P_0 \leq 0.1$ attributed to vapour condensation in nanopores. Interestingly, the *birefringence damping rate* $\Delta w_r / \Delta x_r$ parameter of this isotherm (c.f. Figure 8b) presented a value very close to that of heptane in the bare BBM (see Table 1 and Figure ...), confirming that this parameter depends on the refractive index of the condensed vapour. It is also noteworthy that the VOC adsorption isotherms were not affected by the presence of water vapour in the experimental set up, even at saturation

conditions. In summary, functionalization does not substantially modify the adsorption and condensation capacity of the F-BBM towards VOCs, but prevent the incorporation of water, thus opening the way for the usage of these photonic structures for the selective and quantitative detection of VOCs in environmental conditions and variable degree of humidity.

Figure 8. Optical adsorption isotherms of heptane in the F-BBM measured with a) linear polarized l ($E \perp \mathbf{b}$) and unpolarised light b), as a function of heptane relative partial pressure. c) Plot of the birefringence strength w_r against the filling x_r parameter as a function of heptane partial pressure. d) Schemes of the heptane and water vapour interaction with F-BBM structures.

3. CONCLUSIONS

Previous results and discussion have evidenced the possibility of bestowing optical activity to BBMs prepared by OAD. Unlike the crystalline origin of birefringence in anisotropic single crystals, origin of birefringence in the BBM resides in the anisotropic arrangement, connectivity and size in the nanometric range of the nanocolumnar elements that form the sculptured multilayer structure of the BBM. We have proved that the open void space of the BBM makes easy their interaction with the environment. In particular, we have shown that the exposure of the BBMs to increasing vapor pressure of VOCs can be followed optically through the recording of optical adsorption isotherms. A key specific feature of the BBM is that the strength of their optical activity decreases upon adsorption of increasing amounts of vapor. We have also shown that the variation of the so called *birefringence damping rate* parameter with the pore filling fraction is related to the refractive index of the liquid phase of the adsorbate and, therefore, permits to identify the VOC condensed in the pores. This compound specificity is a singular feature of the BBM and its use might constitute the basis for the future development of vapor modulated birefringent devices.

In the course of this investigation, we have also shown that inner surface of the pores of nanostructured BBM can be functionalized by grafting fluorine containing molecules. This grafting makes them moisture repellent and prevents the adsorption and condensation of water in the pore structure. The high surface tension of water is claimed as the main factor precluding its incorporation into the pores of these F-BBM. However, all other examined VOCs condensed into the functionalized pores where a *birefringent damping rate* parameter similar to that found in the bare BBM could be measured. This result supports the use of the nanostructured F-BBM as optical sensor in ambient conditions where it would not only provide information about the relative pressure of the VOC around, but also a straightforward procedure for its identification.

This work proves that tailoring the birefringence of nanostructured photonic devices through the arrangement of their structural elements at the nanoscale is a powerful method for the development of a new family of photonic devices with tunable/variable optical activity.

4.- MATERIALS AND METHODS

4.1. Fabrication and multilayer structure of porous BBM

The BBMs consist of two porous Bragg mirrors separated by another porous central layer (cavity) whose thickness and refractive index is chosen to open a narrow transmission peak within the mirrors reflection band. The Bragg mirrors were fabricated by the successive stacking of SiO₂ and TiO₂ porous nanocolumnar thin films prepared by OAD electron beam evaporation of SiO₂ or TiO pellets, respectively. The deposition angle was 70°. They had a HLHLHLH multilayer structure, where H/L represents a high/low refractive index layer (i.e., TiO₂/SiO₂). The central cavity consisted of a low refractive index layer. The thicknesses of the nanostructured layers of the Bragg mirrors were about 80 nm, while that of the cavity was about 200 nm. Azimuthally turning the substrate by 180° after each deposited layer rendered a zigzag nanocolumnar microstructure and a homogeneous thickness over relatively large areas. The base pressure of the deposition equipment was 1.0×10⁻⁶ mbar and the process pressure during film growth was adjusted to 2×10⁻⁴ mbar of O₂ through leak of this gas to warrant that nanocolumnar thin films grow transparent (i.e., fully oxidized). The crucible-sample distance was about 50 cm, the deposition rate about 6 nm per minute, and the sample temperature during growth reached values close to 100°C at the substrate position. A more detailed description of the synthesis and some basic characterization analysis of these BBM can be found in a previous publication (6, 8).

4.2. Optical modelling of porous BBM

To reproduce the birefringent behaviour of the porous BBM, we use a parameterized optical model that considers that the individual SiO₂ or TiO₂ stacked layers are birefringent with an uniaxial optical anisotropy where a fast optical axis (low refractive index, $n_{\perp b}$) is in the plane perpendicular to the fence-bundling and a slow optical axis ($n_{\parallel b}$) in the fence-bundling plane (see Figures 1 and Figure S1 in Supporting info file). The in-plane structural birefringence $\Delta n = n_{\parallel b} - n_{\perp b}$ of the individual layers is the result of a difference in material connectivity and therefore polarizability, along these two orthogonal planes. In a previous work [6,8], we obtained values for the in-plane birefringence of 0.30 and 0.05 refractive index units for the individual TiO₂ and SiO₂ deposited layers, respectively. The absolute values of the refractive index of the individual layers were consistent with 33% and 40% void fractions in the bundling and

orthogonal directions, respectively. This assessment stems from a Maxwell-Garnett effective medium approximation (34) applied independently to each main optical axis. The same approximation was used to simulate the pore filling by vapours adsorption and condensation, whereby we considered a kind of composite material formed by a compact media (i.e., either TiO_2 or SiO_2) and voids which can be either empty or partially/completely filled with condensed vapours with a given refractive index. For these calculations, we have assumed that both H and L layers have the same percentage of pore volume. This hypothesis is consistent with the fence-bundling association of nanocolumns observed in these BBM. The wavelength dispersion of the refractive index of the individual layers was described with a typical Cauchy law.

4.3. Experimental setup for optical adsorption isotherm measurements

The scheme of the experimental set-up used for the measurements of the optical adsorption isotherms is shown in **Figure S5**. It consists of an adsorption chamber provided with pumping and vapour dosing systems and the optics required to characterize the samples in transmission geometry. BBM sample was placed in-between the line of sight of two fibre optic collimators linked to optical fibre feedthroughs. The light beam inside the chamber had 6 mm diameter. Illumination was made with a halogen light source (DH-2000, Ocean Optics) at normal incidence and transmitted light analysis done with a spectroscopic monochromator (Maya2000-Pro, Ocean Optics). For some experiments, a polarizer was placed inside the chamber between the incident light beam and the sample, aligned either perpendicular or parallel to the fence-bundling directions of the BBM.

The procedure to measure the optical adsorption isotherms was as follows. The adsorption chamber was evacuated up to a base pressure of 10^{-2} mbar while the sample was heated to 50 °C during 20 minutes to remove any water adsorbed in the pores due to ambient air exposure. After evacuation, the chamber connection with the pumping system was closed. The vapour dosing system, made of a series of valves separating a defined volume V_p , allows increasing the pressure P in the chamber in fixed steps. Vapour volume V_p at a saturation pressure P_0 in equilibrium with the liquid present in a bulb, previously evacuated applying several freeze-pump-thaw degassing cycles, was expanded to the volume of the chamber rendering a pressure P as determined by a measuring gauge. Pressure in the adsorption chamber P varied from 0 to the saturation pressure P_0 , in a series of successive steps. The chamber was kept at a fixed temperature of $\sim 40^\circ\text{C}$ during

the complete adsorption process, while the sample was kept at 25 °C. This difference in temperature precludes any uncontrolled vapour condensation in a cold zone of the system. Optical adsorption isotherms were obtained plotting the position of the resonant peak or its full width at half maximum (FWHM) as a function of the relative vapour pressure expressed as the P/P_0 ratio. It is noteworthy that the adsorption/desorption of the condensed vapours was in all cases completely reversible and that it suffices a prolonged pumping to remove any spectral hint of vapour condensation from a previous adsorption experiment in the BBM.

Note that transmittance spectra are represented against photon energy units (i.e., eV) instead of wavelength (i.e., nm) to minimise the well-known increase of width of the interference fringes as the wavelength increases. Besides, when series of spectra recorded at different P/P_0 values are plotted in the same figure, the measured transmittance has been normalized to make the analysis independent of spurious intensity fluctuations.

4.4. Pore surface functionalization and characterization

Pore surface functionalization was carried out by grafting the 1H,1H,2H,2H-perfluorooctyltriethoxysilane (PFOTES) molecule. A Scheme of this molecule in its grafted state is reported in the supporting information **Figure S6**. Grafted F-BBM samples were prepared by derivatization. The procedure consisted of exposing the BBM for three hours *to the* vapour of this molecule placed in a bath at 80°C. Prior to the dosage of the PFOTES vapours, the BBM were activated by prolonged exposure to a soft plasma of oxygen provided by a microwave ERC source working in a remote configuration at 4×10^{-3} Torr.

The surface functionalization of the BBM samples was characterised by elemental depth profile measurements acquired on a K-Alpha XPS spectrometer equipped with a MAGCIS dual beam ion source (Thermo Scientific, East Grinstead, UK). The sample was etched with a 4 keV monatomic Ar ion beam, raster scanning an area 2x4 mm. The XPS measurements were acquired over an analysis area 400 micrometre in diameter centred inside the raster scanned area, using charge compensation. The sample was etched for a total 21433 sec. alternating etching cycles with XPS spectra acquisition. The first 290 sec. were an exploratory etching using the instrument low ion current mode (instrument nominal etching rate 0.09 nm s^{-1} on Ta₂O₅ reference material), switching to

high ion current mode (instrument nominal etching rate 0.26 nm s^{-1} on Ta_2O_5 reference material) for the rest of the measurement, the first data point in the depth profile corresponding to the pristine surface. On each XPS acquisition step, snapshots of the Si 2p, C 1s, Ti 2p and F 1s regions were acquired. XPS spectra were analysed using CasaXPS (Casa Software Ltd, Teignmouth, UK) by removing backgrounds with a Shirley model and applying Scofield cross-sections for extracting relative atomic percentages from the peak areas.

Acknowledgements

Authors thank the EU Cohesion Fund program (FEDER) and AEI-MICINN (PID2019-110430GB-C21), CSIC (2019AEP161, CSIC 201860E050) and Junta de Andalucía (PAIDI-2020 through projects P18-RT-3480 and ref. 6079) for financial support.

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SUPPORTING INFO

Nanostructured birefringent resonant transducers for the selective monitoring of VOCs in ambient conditions

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Figure S1. Schemes of the nanostructure of thin films prepared by oblique angle PVD. Left) Cross section view of the films along a plane perpendicular to the deposition plane. The scheme includes the main direction of arrival of deposited vapour flux and the normal to the substrate surface and shows the formation of a tilted nanocolumnar nanostructure. Right) Cross section view of the films along a plane parallel View r to the deposition plane showing the fence-bundling direction

Figure S2. Left panel: Optical adsorption isotherms acquired with unpolarised light showing the mean position x_r (left axis) and FWHM w_r (right axis) of the resonant peak of a BBM as methanol (a), ethanol (b), heptane (c), chloroform (d), and toluene (e) partial pressure increases. Right column: Plots of w_r against x_r as methanol (a'), ethanol (b'), heptane (c'), chloroform (d'), and toluene (e') vapor partial pressures increase. The experimental birefringence damping rate parameters $\Delta w_r / \Delta x_r$ obtained for each adsorbed vapour are indicated.

Figure S3. Optical adsorption isotherms acquired with polarized light ($E \perp \mathbf{b}$) showing the mean position $x_{r\perp}$ (left axis) and FWHM $w_{r\perp}$ (right axis) of the resonant peak for a BBM exposed to increasing partial pressures of heptane part.

Figure S4. a) Evolution as a function of filling fraction of the filling rates of pores along optical axis aligned parallel (left) and perpendicular (right) to the bundling direction for

the three simulation models considered (open circles: one-stage; open squares: two-stages-2.0; full triangles: two-stages-1.3) b) Model predictions of the mean position x_r (left axis) and FWHM w_r (right axis) of the resonant peak as the filling fraction increases according to the three simulation models.

Figure S5. Scheme of the optical adsorption isotherm set-up system. c_1, c_2 : fibre optic collimators; p : linear polarizer; s : sample; V_p : “expansion volume”.

Figure S6. Schemes of the molecular structure of PFOTES molecule before (left) and after (right) surface grafting

Graphical abstract

(para que sirva de inspiración, lo he cogido de otro trabajo)

